

Producing comfort: Phobia based design and its emotional impact on the fear of darkness.

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Introduction

This case study proposes phobia based design as means to comfort people with debilitating phobias. Phobia based design can be understood as a user centred design method. Starting point of the design process is the phobic user's needs. In the study an impact of experimental products on the fear of darkness (i.e. achluophobia, lygophobia, myctophobia, noctiphobia, nyctophobia or scotophobia) is probed.

Why phobia design approach? Tests with phobic patients by using computer games and virtual reality equipment have showed, that the responses stimulated in virtual reality could be used to perform controlled treatment (Renaud, 2004). User experiment presented further on aims to show how haptic, functional products can be used as comfort producers in a moment of fear.

The phobia based design case presented is part of a larger product concept called "*Place*". It includes several items, experimental products and conceptual idea of a future shopping environment. The concept "*Place*" is a Master of Art thesis for the University of Art and Design Helsinki from year 2005. The concept was presented to a larger audience in 2 promotional exhibitions: Designmai 2005 in Berlin and Masters of Arts 2005 festival in Helsinki (images 1-3).

As considering phobia design viewpoint only the relevant part of the "*Place*" concept was chosen for closer examination for this study. That is the design case "*A place to dream*". The motivation for the design case arose from the curiosity to test phobia based design concretely. "*A place to dream*" is a combination of experimental products which emit light in the dark. After design process a small scale user test was conducted to evaluate the product qualities and to find justifications for the claim that the products have an emotional impact on the fear of darkness.

Image 1.

"Brave New Worlds – Design for a Better Future?" was the focal topic of DESIGNMAI 2005. It aimed to examine what answers design and designers have to issues impacting the future." (www.designmai.de, 2005)

Image 2.

DESIGNMAI 2005.

Photo documentation by Kilian-Davy Baujard, Jens Vogt, the DESIGNMAI 2005 participants and their friends.

Masters of Arts 2005 Festival
Media Centre Lume May 11th – 27th

Image 3.

“Masters of Arts festival in University of Art and Design Helsinki creates a scene for the new masters to get their ideas, expertise and visions to be seen and heard by the large audience, media, professionals, decision makers and future employers.”

(www.uiah.fi/moa2005)

Aim and purpose

The purpose of the presentation is to stimulate discussion on a theme of phobia design and about designers' new social assignments.

The project example presented aims to find reasoning for the claim that functional products can be comforting as one experiences a phobia, if the product function meets the user need in a moment of the fear.

Most people experience unpleasant emotions often, if not daily. These emotions cannot be called phobias and should not be eliminated from every day life. Some of the negative emotions notify of social, environmental, physiological and mental changes. The design case was targeted to users who suffer from a fear regularly.

The design case

“A place to dream”

Firstly experimental products from the fear of darkness basis were designed, secondly the products were presented in promotional design exhibitions among other products, and thirdly a user test was conducted.

In creation of the whole product concept “*Place*” several individuals and companies were involved. “*A place to dream*” was designed in collaboration with interior designer Klaus Aalto who helped designing the space screen divider and was the exhibition architect for the Berlin “*Place*” exhibition in Designmai 2005. The light emitting “*A place to dream*” products were made in a design studio (images 4-8). These blankets and space screen dividers are knitted and woven, store the day or artificial light, and emit light in the dark.

The identification of an imaginary end user Frau Müller was used for recognising the phobic user’s needs. The design process was based on her fear of darkness. If one becomes aware of people’s backgrounds, their current situation, living conditions, and future hopes such information can make the user needs visible for the design work (Hailahti, 2005). By designing for the user needs the products’ aim was to produce comfort. Easing her phobia was the reason to design. After need recognition the idea of designing light emitting products became a clear option. Designing was thus based on selecting needs of the user from the story and on making the function concrete in the products.

In phobia based designing some factors of emphatic design are beneficial. Koskinen and Battarbee discuss how it is important to trust the research data and not value the interpretation too high (Koskinen, Battarbee, 2003). They also underline that understanding the user is essential. If a design solution is offered for a phobia, first step for a designer is to understand the situation the user is experiencing as the phobia arises. After the design process a user test

was conducted to evaluate was the user understood and did the solutions designed have an impact on the fear of darkness.

Discussion

The project example achieved to find reasoning for the claim functional products being comforting on a moment of a fear of darkness. The main purpose of the user test was probing the relationship between phobic user and experimental products. It was needed for learning about the users' emotional experiences. A family with child aged 7 and an adult aged 35 were chosen as subjects for the study. Both, the child and the adult, had a fear of darkness which interrupted their normal way of living. Either of the subjects suffered pathological fear, but they had regular problems with darkness. Subjects were given two products: a blanket and a space screen divider both with light emitting material function (images 4-8). For 5 days the subjects used the products. After the test period they were interviewed on did they experience darkness differently as using the products and did the products have a comforting impact on their fear of darkness.

The users' responses were positive. Both of them felt the products eased their fear in the dark room. The products helped them falling into a sleep better. The adult described them as comforting nightlights. The 7 year old's named the space screen divider 'a friendly ghost'. They had formed the functional metal material with the family into a ghost form. Obviously, if the product was not functioning well it did not satisfy the user and caused a frustration. This happened with the adult user once. The user had the blanket fouled up and the material did not have enough light to emit in the dark, because it did not receive any during the day.

This small study demonstrated that products can make a difference for one suffering from a fear. Therefore the aim was achieved. Further studies would be needed to evaluate phobic user's product attachment and therapeutic treatment for pathological fear. The design process itself could be improved. Involving the users in the design process already in the first phase and committing them to give insights on their fear would support the design process. For example interviewing and observing the target users, more specifically diary studies and contextual inquiries with artifact interviews would help to create an overview of the user and user situations in relation to the phobia before designing (adapted from the workshop process by Battarbee, Mattelmäki, Mäkelä, 2001). To design product solutions for more challenging phobias than fear of darkness, that overview would be necessary information.

Image 4.

"A Place to dream"

Glowing wool blanket. Photo: Hannaliisa Hailahti.

Images 5 and 6.

“A Place to dream”

Knitted, light emitting woollen textiles. Photo: Sampo Korhonen.

Images 7 and 8.

“A Place to dream”

Woven light emitting interior fabric, a space screen divider, is a comfort producer for phobic a user. It also guides the inhabitant in a dark room. It can be reformed by the user again and again because of its metal structure. Therefore a user can play with it, shape it into any form again and again. Photo: Sampo Korhonen.

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